

An interdisciplinary tutorial:
building your own self-healing soft finger with embedded
sensor

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Introduction

This document guides you to build your own self-healing soft finger with embedded sensor, step-by-step. The tutorial is divided in four parts: synthesis of the self-healing polymer, moulding of the soft finger, testing the robotic system, and healing. Before starting, it is recommended to read the whole document first, including the paper that discusses the background of this tutorial.

To successfully follow the tutorial, several tools are needed. Most of them are common and/or inexpensive, with the only notable exception being a vacuum chamber which costs around 150 euro. A full list of tools is given in table 1.

Table 1: List of required tools.

<i>Tools</i>	
<input type="checkbox"/> Lab coat	<input type="checkbox"/> Gloves
<input type="checkbox"/> Ruler	<input type="checkbox"/> Scale 0.01 g
<input type="checkbox"/> Cutting board	<input type="checkbox"/> Recipient
<input type="checkbox"/> Scalpel	<input type="checkbox"/> Spatula
<input type="checkbox"/> Pliers	<input type="checkbox"/> Cleaning paper
<input type="checkbox"/> Multimeter	<input type="checkbox"/> Vacuum chamber
<input type="checkbox"/> Flathead screwdriver	<input type="checkbox"/> Oven

Besides tools, some additional materials are needed. Table 2 gives the bill of materials for this tutorial. Many items can be bought in conventional hardware stores, or online. The reagents BMI1400, 4TBC, and FT3000, as well as the sensor fibres, can be obtained by contacting the authors via ellen.roels@vub.be.

The mould set and motor holder clamping piece need to be fabricated. They can be made using common maker space tools. The mould set is preferably made using an SLA 3D-printer, but can also be 3D-printed using FFF or machined (CNC). The material should be heat resistant up to 90°C (except the part **motor holder set/clamping piece** that is used in the motor holder). The motor holder set can be fabricated easily using a laser cutter. The design is made for a 3 mm thick sheet, but can be adapted. Alternatively, these parts can also be made using a 3D-printer or machined. Note that the part ‘side’ is needed twice.

Following the complete tutorial from start to finish is not possible in a single day, as the material needs time to cure and rest after healing. Therefore, when using this tutorial as a short workshop, several steps should be prepared in advance. For example, a sensor and a full finger can be given to the participants so they can continue without waiting for the material to cure. Also the last step of the healing procedure can be omitted.

Table 2: Bill of materials for the tutorial.

Item	Amount
<i>Synthesis</i>	
Bismaleimide BMI1400	6 g
Radical inhibitor 4TBC	0.06 g
Polyfuran resin FT3000	9 g ^a
Acetone	a few ml
Sheet of paper	1
Pipette (plastic)	1
<i>Fabrication</i>	
SH sensor fibre	18 cm ^a
Jumper wires	9
Mould set	1 ^a
M3 nut	18
Bolt M3x10	3
Bolt M3x40	4
Release agent	a bit
Copper (hook up) wire	30 cm
Molex Mini-Fit Female Crimp Terminal	2
Nylon wire (diameter 0.5 mm)	30 cm
PTFE tubing (ID 0.8 mm, OD 1.6 mm)	10cm
<i>Testing the robotic system</i>	
Motor holder set	1 ^a
Servo motor	1
Bolt M3x8	12
Bolt M3x14	2
Arduino nano + USB cable	1
Resistor	1
Breadboard	1

^aMade in-house.

Chapter 1

Synthesis of the self-healing polymer

When working with chemicals, always wear appropriate personal protection equipment, such as a lab coat and lab gloves, and work in a well-ventilated place. Read the material safety data sheets and follow the instructions carefully. When touching the liquid materials, wash your hands thoroughly with soap.

Step 1: Preheat oven

1. Preheat the oven to 90 °C.

Step 2: Calculate the reagents

1. Open the attached spreadsheet `synthesis.ods`.
2. The polymer used for this tutorial has a stoichiometric ratio of $r=0.5$, change this in cell D3.
3. To make the complete finger, you will need to make 11 g of material. However, the synthesis will be done in two parts: 3 g for the sensor and 8 g for the finger. Make only 3 g for now. Add this in cell D4.
4. Take note of the amount of maleimide (BMI1400), inhibitor (4-tert-butylcatechol) and furan (FT3000) needed. You should find:

maleimide 1.15 g

inhibitor 0.01 g

furan 1.85 g

Write the amount of reagents on a piece of paper, so you can keep your computer away from the reagents during the synthesis.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1									
2		BMI1400 - JT3000			Unit		Reagents	Molar Masses (M [*])	Unit
3		Desired Stoichiometric ratio	r	0.5	/		BMI1400	859.5	g/mol
4		Desired amount	m tot (g)	3	g		FT3000	690.6	g/mol
5			m Maleimide (g)	1.151	g				
6			m Furan (g)	1.849	g				
7			m 4-tert-butylcatechol	0.0115	g				
8									

Step 3: Weigh the maleimide

1. Take an empty recipient (e.g. glass or plastic beaker) and tare it on the balance. (a)

Make sure the recipient is big enough, as the mixture will expand during degassing later.

2. Take a clean spatula.
3. Put the correct amount (1.15 g) of maleimide (BMI 1400) in the recipient using the spatula. (b)
4. Clean the spatula using acetone and paper.

Acetone might damage your gloves. Be careful and replace them when damaged.

(a)

(b)

Step 4: Weigh the inhibitor

1. Take a piece of clean (printer) paper.
2. Fold it in two lengthwise and open the fold again.
3. Fold it along the other side, and open the fold again. You should have obtained a small cup shape. (a)
4. Place the paper on the scale and tare it.
5. Take a clean spatula.
6. Using the spatula, weigh the required amount (0.01 g) of inhibitor on the paper. (b)
7. Add the inhibitor to the maleimide.

Step 5: Dissolve the inhibitor in the maleimide

1. Place the recipient filled with maleimide and inhibitor in the oven at 90°C.
2. Wait until the inhibitor is dissolved, this should only take a few minutes.
3. Take the recipient out of the oven with heat-resistant gloves.

Step 6: Add the furan

1. Place the recipient on the scale and tare. (a)
2. Using a pipette, add the required amount of furan (1.85 g) to the mixture. (b)
3. Mix the mixture for 5 minutes using a clean spatula. Make sure to also take the material sticking to the edges. The mixture will become opaque because air bubbles are formed. (c)
4. Clean the spatula using acetone and paper.

Step 7: Degas the mixture

1. Place the recipient in the vacuum chamber. (a)
2. Follow the instructions of your device to slowly achieve vacuum. (b)

If the material risks overflowing, increase the pressure a bit and continue slowly.

3. Leave the mixture at vacuum until almost no more bubbles are visible.
4. Slowly increase the pressure and take the mixture out. It will have become less opaque. (c)

From the moment it is mixed, the polymer starts to react. You have about 90 minutes to mould it.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Chapter 2

Moulding of the soft finger

Step 1: Prepare the self-healing sensor fibre

1. Measure and cut a piece of 18 cm of the sensor fibre. (a)

Only tighten the fibre while measuring, do not stretch it.

2. Take two crimp connectors and pliers. (b)
3. Place one end of the fibre in a connector.
4. Crimp the connector tightly around the fibre using pliers. ((c-e)

Avoid pushing too hard as the fibre can break off.

5. Repeat the crimping process on the other end of the fibre. (f)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Step 2: Measure the resistance

1. Take the multi-meter, and select the resistance measurement (this is usually indicated with Ω). (a)
2. Make sure the fibre is not touching itself.
3. Connect a probe to each of the crimp connectors. (b)
4. Read the resistance from the screen, it should be between 50-500 k Ω .

(a)

(b)

Step 3: Place the fibre in the mould

1. Take the sensor mould and place a 10 mm long M3 bolt in each hole such that it sticks out a bit. (a)
2. Slide one of the connectors in a small channel at the edge of the mould. (b)

Using a flathead screwdriver or tweezers can make this easier.

3. Route the fibre around the screws, and place the second connector in the other small channel. (c)
4. Push the fibre down at the screws so it sits almost at the bottom of the mould. (d-e)
5. Check the resistance of the fibre again using the procedure from step 2. The resistance should not have changed dramatically. (f)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Step 4: Mould the sensor

1. Pour the material mixture gently inside of the mould and let it spread evenly. (a)
2. Place the mould in the preheated oven to speed up the reaction. (b)
3. After 90 min, take the mould out of the oven and slowly let it cool down to room temperature for 45 minutes.

Step 5: Unmould the sensor

1. Carefully remove the screws from the mould. (a)
2. Using the spatula or flathead screwdriver, gently remove the sensor from the mould. (b-c)

This step is easiest when you start from the tip of the sensor and slowly work your way towards the connectors. (d)

3. Attach a jumper wire to each crimp connector.

Step 6: Assemble the mould for the finger

1. Take the three finger mould parts, 4 40 mm M3 bolts, and 4 M3 nuts. (a)
2. Place the middle part of the mould on the bottom, and put a screw through the four corners with the threaded side facing upwards. (b)
3. Cut about 30 cm of the copper wire.
4. Route the wire all the way through the mould using the holes at the sides. (c)

Step 7: Mould the finger

1. Prepare 8 g of material following the procedure of 1.
2. Spray the mould with release agent.
3. Place the sensor in the mould with the connectors at the thinnest side of the finger, pointing upwards. (a)
4. Verify that the mould is assembled well and there are no gaps at the bottom.
5. Pour the material mixture carefully in the mould, until it is full. (b)
6. Place the cables through the hole in the top part of the mould. (c)

Make sure the top part of the mould is oriented in the correct direction.

7. Close the mould using the top part. (d)
8. Place nuts on the mould screws and tighten them.
9. Pour some extra material in the channel of the top mould part, until it is filled completely. (e)
10. Check back after a minute. If the material level has decreased, pour some extra material in the channel.
11. Place the mould in the preheated oven to speed up the reaction. (f)
12. After 90 min, take the mould out of the oven and slowly let it cool down to room temperature for 45 minutes.

Step 8: Unmould the finger

1. Pull the copper wire out of the mould.
2. Detach the nuts and take out the screws. (a)
3. Open the mould by prying a screwdriver between the bottom and middle part of the mould to separate them. (b)
4. Remove the bottom part from the mould. (c)
5. Slide the middle part from top of the mould. (d)

Use a screwdriver to separate them if needed, but try to stay away from the cables.

6. Gently remove the finger from the top part of the mould. (e-f)

Step 9: Prepare the finger for testing

1. Cut four pieces of about 2 cm from the PTFE (teflon) tubing.
2. Place the PTFE tubes in the holes of the phalanges.
3. Cut 30 cm from the nylon wire.
4. Route the tendon wire through the PTFE tubes. (a)
5. At the tip of the finger, make a few knots in the wire so it can no longer slide into the tube. (b)

Alternatively, route the wire through a small washer, and make a knot to secure it in place.

(a)

(b)

Chapter 3

Testing the robotic system

Step 1: Assemble the set-up

1. Screw the servo motor to the top plate of the set-up using 4 8 mm M3 screws and nuts. Verify that the servo motor is in the correct orientation. (a)
2. Connect one side of the setup to the top plate. Place a nut in one of the slots in the top plate and hold it in place while inserting the screw. Then repeat the procedure for the other screw. Do not tighten the screws all the way. Use 8 mm long M3 screws to assemble the set-up. (b)
3. Connect the bottom plate to the assembly using two screws in the same way. Do not tighten the screw all the way. (c)
4. Add the second side plate and fasten it with 4 screws.
5. Tighten all the screws. (d)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Step 2: Prepare electronic components

1. Prepare the servo set-up, breadboard, Arduino nano, and jumper wires.

2. Measure the resistance of the sensor.
3. Select a resistor whose resistance is in the same order of magnitude as the sensor. In case of doubt, take a lower value.

For the next step, a breadboard is used. This is a prototyping board for electronics. It is usually divided in two parts. When held vertically (so there is a left and a right part, rather than top and bottom), the holes in the rows of each part are internally connected using a metal strip. Some breadboards have bus strips on the side, designated with + and - to indicate the supply voltage and ground. The pins of each of the bus columns are also internally connected.

Step 3: Wire the electronics

1. Place the Arduino nano over the middle of the breadboard.

Failing to do so will cause a short circuit and damage the electronics.

2. Make the following scheme on the breadboard.
3. Verify the correctness of the scheme.

Step 4: Program the Arduino

1. Download and install the Arduino IDE. This free and open source software can be downloaded from <https://www.arduino.cc/en/software>.
2. Open the Arduino IDE.
3. The file tutorial.ino can be downloaded. It has a lot of explanatory comments (preceded by //).
4. In the code, change the resistor value on line 7 to the value of the resistor you selected.

Step 5: Upload the code to the Arduino

1. Connect the Arduino to your computer using a USB cable.
2. In the software, go to Tools → Port, and select the COM port that corresponds to the Arduino. Normally, there will only be one option. (a)
3. Select the Arduino nano from Tools → Board. (b)
4. Upload the code to the Arduino using the arrow button. (c)

If the upload fails, and you are not working with an official Arduino, it might be that it uses a different chipset. In that case, you have to select ATmega328 (Old Bootloader) from the menu under Tools → Processor. Also, you might need to install an extra driver which can be downloaded from the tutorial files.

5. Verify that the servo motor is turning to 90° and back.
6. Unplug the USB cable.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Step 6: Clamp the finger to the set-up

1. Rotate the servo motor to the 0° position.
2. Place the finger on the set-up with the phalanges facing upwards in between the holes. (a)

Temporarily disconnect the finger from the breadboard if that is easier to work with. Don't forget to reconnect it afterwards.

3. Take the plastic holder piece and place it over the finger. It has a cutout on the bottom for the connectors. Make sure that the tendon wire is routed above the piece. (b-c))
4. Fasten the finger under the piece with two 14 mm long M3screws and nuts. (d)

Step 7: Connect the tendon wire to the servo motor

1. Hold the finger horizontally.
2. Route the tendon wire from bottom to top through the closest hole of the servo. (a)
3. Route the tendon wire from top to bottom through the second closest hole of the servo motor.
4. Put just enough tension on the wire such that the finger almost starts bending, and tie a double knot to secure it. (b)
5. Cut the remaining tendon wire.

Step 8: Measure the sensor signal

1. Replug the USB cable from the Arduino to the computer. The finger now starts moving back and forth.

2. Open the serial plotter from the Arduino IDE under Tools → serial plotter, or use ctrl+shift/L to open it. (a)
3. The sensor signal will show on the plot (b)

(a)

(b)

Chapter 4

Healing

Step 1: Disconnect the finger from the set-up

1. Unplug the USB cable of the Arduino.
2. Unplug the finger from the breadboard.
3. Untie the knots of the tendon wire and remove it from the servo motor.
4. Unscrew the plastic holder piece that is clamping the finger, and remove the finger from the set-up.

Step 2: Damage the finger

1. Measure the resistance of the sensor and write it down. (a)
2. Using a sharp blade, cut the finger and sensor in two. Try to make a clean cut. (b)

(a)

(b)

Step 3: Heal the finger

1. Place the two pieces back together so they make contact. Try to avoid misalignment.
2. Measure the resistance.

3. If the resistance is in the same order of magnitude as before, it is making good contact. If not, change the alignment until the resistance shows the correct value.
4. Place the finger in the oven at 90°C.
5. Take it out of the oven after 45 minutes, and let it cool down to room temperature slowly.

Step 4: Test the healed finger

1. After the finger is cooled down to room temperature, leave it to rest at room temperature for at least 5 hours.
2. It should now be healed, and the testing procedure using the Arduino can be repeated.